

EFFICACY OF TOPICAL INSULIN GEL DRESSING VERSUS COLLAGEN DRESSING IN TREATING FACIAL SOFT TISSUE ABRASIONS: A SPLIT FACE CLINICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate the efficacy of topical insulin gel dressing versus collagen membrane dressing in managing facial soft tissue abrasions.in Civil Hospital Hingoli and Subdistrict hospital hingoli. **Objectives:** To formulate topical insulin gel and to assess and compare the efficacy of topical insulin gel and collagen dressings. **Methods:** A total of 52 patients with bilateral and multiple facial abrasions were included in this study. A split face design experimental study was conducted using topical insulin gel and collagen dressing. Rate of wound healing and epithelization, reduction of wound size and complications were assessed and compared among the two groups over a period of 21 days. **Results:** A statistically significant result was found in the insulin dressing site during initial days of wound healing. While both the dressing materials effectively reduced the wound size by 21 days, suggesting that

both the dressing materials are effective in wound healing with minor differences in the initial response. Scarring was seen more in collagen dressing group compared to insulin gel group.

Conclusion: Both the dressing materials were effective in reduction of wound size over the time but insulin gel dressings showed slightly superior quality of healing in terms of scar and texture when compared to other.

KEYWORDS: Wound healing · Insulin dressing · Topical insulin gel · Collagen dressing · Re-epithelization · Granulation tissue.

INTRODUCTION

Soft tissue injuries are the most common injuries occurring frequently in the head and neck region, especially on the face following road traffic accidents and other injuries.

Frequently seen facial soft tissue injuries include simple lacerations, abrasions, contusions, bites, avulsions, and burns. Among these, abrasions are the most common of all the soft tissue injuries that results in destruction of superficial layers of the skin involving epidermis and dermis caused by frictional forces.^[1] Soft tissue abrasions involving partial thickness dermal injury may not be surgically closed and can be addressed with debridement, wound irrigation and appropriate dressings to achieve esthetic outcomes and to minimize the complications such as infections, hematomas, or excessive new tissue formation.

The ideal dressing should achieve rapid, adequate, scar free healing and anti-inflammatory action available at affordable cost and ease in procurement by the patient. Wide range of modern dressing materials are in use currently for the management of wounds such as parafin gauze, collagen membrane, chitosan, amniotic membrane, fish skin, and dermal autograft. Polyurethane dressings with incorporated drugs such as antimicrobial agents, enzymes and growth factors like EGF, TGF- α , TGF- β , PDGF, IGF etc. are used to improve the wound healing process and to stimulate faster skin regeneration.^[2] One of the dressing materials which gained popularity in recent times is collagen membrane and is being used on a regular basis in the management of facial soft tissue injuries. Collagen is a fibrous protein that is found in the skin, bones, tendons, cartilages, blood vessels, and teeth. Due to its simple form and manageability, it is commonly utilized in the field of medicine. Collagen, which is the body's most abundant protein, plays a crucial role in the completion of wound healing because of its bioactive, resorbable properties and ability to support cell growth. Its low antigenicity, anti-inflammatory response and its ability to stay stable for several weeks makes it an effective biocompatible dressing material for soft tissue repair.^[3] Over decades topical insulin was known for its clinical benefits in wound healing and used in dressings for diabetic foot ulcers and pressure ulcers showing faster wound healing rate without any systemic reduction in blood sugar levels.^[4] It has been discovered that insulin, a peptide hormone with a variety of physiological functions, has good wound healing qualities as it increases the growth and development of keratinocytes, endothelial cells and fibroblast proliferation as well as migration of cells and the secretion process.^[5] It can repair damaged skin and is less expensive than other growth factors. Furthermore, it helps in the regulation of energy

metabolism and protein synthesis.^[6] Paucity of literature on insulin dressing and its formulation for facial soft tissue abrasions has led to conducting this split face comparative study between insulin gel dressing and colla-gen membrane dressing materials.^[7] Hence, the current study deals with the formulation of topical insulin gel and its application on facial abrasions along with comparing the efectiveness of insulin gel over collagen membrane.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this split face design experimental study, a total of 52 patients with Garde I and Grade II facial abrasions due to road traf c accidents reporting to the casualty of Ramaiah group of hospitals and Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department, Faculty of Dental Sciences, RUAS, Bangalore, from August 2022 to February 2024 were enrolled. Among them 13 were females and 39 were males. Grade I and Grade II facial abrasions zones were included in this study. Patients with severe tissue loss, systemic condition/systemic drugs that hampers healing of wound and patients with missed follow-ups during the treatment were excluded from the study.

This study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences and written Inform consent was obtained after explaining the treatment protocol to the patients.

All patients were subjected to both insulin gel and col- lagen membrane dressing by dividing the wound in such a way that, if there was unilateral single abraded wound— it was divided into two equal halves, where insulin gel was applied over upper portion and collagen membrane in the lower portion of the wound, in case of unilateral multiple wounds, then it was divided into equal upper half with insulin gel and lower half of face with collagen membrane. In case of bilateral facial wounds, collagen membrane was applied on the left side, and insulin gel application was done on right-side to avoid operator bias (Fig. 1). If patients reported with diferential grading of soft tissue injuries, only Grade I and Grade II abrasion zones were selected for the study and rest was managed as Fig. 1 a Images showing Insulin dressing, b Collagen dressing and c Both the dressing materials standard protocol like suturing, grafting and anti- scar cream applications, etc.

Thorough debridement of facial wounds was done using hydrogen peroxide 6% w/v and sterile normal saline (0.9% NaCl) before application of dressing materials.

Collagen Site

Commercially available bovine collagen membrane was soaked in normal saline to wash of the preservatives and cut into desirable sizes and applied over the wound surface and left in situ till the epithelization takes place. Re-application of collagen membrane was done only if the wound site got infected or it was accidentally dislodged. It was maintained by cleaning with saline and application of skin antiseptic ointment on its surface and wounds were assessed at day 0, day 03, day 07, day 14 and day 21. (Fig. 1b).

Insulin Site

Since the retention ability of the liquid insulin on the wound surface is questionable, we preferred to convert it into a gel form for its better retention and adherence on the facial wound by mixing the commercially available biphasic isophane insulin 30:70 (Human Mixtard) which is a combination of short-acting and intermediate acting insulin with the bioinert gelling agents.

Preparation of Topical Insulin Gel (100g)

Topical insulin gel was prepared using biphasic isophane insulin in the form of gel with 5% w/v gel base in 1:1 ratio using Carbopol (ultrez 10). 2gms of Carbopol was added to water and stirred for a period of 30 min until it dispersed. Later, about 20 ml of insulin (Human insulin 40 IU/ ml) was added drop wise using a sterile syringe to the Carbopol dispersion under cool temperature by immersing the container in the ice bath and pH was adjusted between 6.14 and 6.7 using 1% sodium hydroxide solution. As the temperature shifted to neutral, it resulted in crystal-clear gel. The freshly prepared gel was used for up to 2–4 weeks by preserving it in the refrigerator.

The prepared insulin gel has half-life of 8–9 h with bioactivity up to 24 h. It was applied on the wound surface once daily via luer lock syringe. About 1 cc of gel was applied on the wound surface and then covered with sterile Jelonet dressing sheet (Fig. 1a). Wounds were assessed and measured with a sterile disposable measuring scale and sterile thread on day 0, day 03, day 07, day 14, and day 21. The greatest diameters along its length and width were measured in centimeters to calculate the wound area.^[8] The study endpoint was considered once the epithelial tissue formation was complete.^[9]

Wound healing was assessed by evidence of granulation tissue and epithelialization from the adjacent normal skin in the stipulated time as mentioned above in both the sites (Fig. 2a–c).

The rate of wound healing was calculated as the difference between the initial wound size on the first day (day 0) and after complete wound healing which was recorded in terms of cm² / week. Vancouver scar scale by (Draaijers et.al) was used to assess the scar in four domains: vascularity, pigmentation, pliability and height.

The scores were ranged from 0 to 13, and the maximum score of 13 was considered as worst prognosis.^[1,10]

Fig. 2 a, b, c Images showing wound healing of insulin dressing(left) and collagen dressing(right) after 7 days.

Statistical Analysis

Since the data were not normally distributed in this study, nonparametric tests were used as tests for normality and the results were analyzed using the Wilcoxon signed- rank test to compare the healing rates between insulin gel and collagen dressing and Chi-square test was used for comparing complications such as bleeding, wound infection and scarring between the two groups.

RESULTS

A total of 52 patients, who fulfill the inclusion criteria were enrolled in this study, out of which 13 were females and 39 were males. The mean age of the participants of the study was 30.63 years. According to split face experimental study design, all patients included in the study were subjected to both the dressings, i.e., collagen and insulin, and followed up for 21 days at periodic intervals as mentioned (Table 1). The complications such as bleeding, infection and scarring were assessed during the follow-up period.

The insulin site demonstrated a greater reduction in wound area in the initial days, and this trend persisted through days seven and fourteen, with insulin gel consistently showing a faster reduction in the wound area as compared with collagen dressing. By day twenty-one, both the treatments resulted in complete wound closure, indicating similar long-term effectiveness (Table 2).

The rate of wound healing in insulin gel dressing was much faster with 4.54 median healing rate (with a high standard deviation of 4.32) while the collagen dressing had a healing rate of 2.19 (with a lower standard deviation of 1.1) (Table 3). The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted to compare the healing rates between insulin gel and collagen dressing which

revealed statistically significant difference ($P=0.00$), suggestive of much higher healing rate in insulin gel site as compared to collagen dressing site.

None of the wound site had active bleeding but blood-tinged serosanguinous ooze was observed in 12 cases (23.1%) in the collagen dressing site that was assessed by soakage of the dressing and required change of collagen dressings the very next day, and as well in 8 cases (15.4%) in the insulin dressing site. Notably, neither of the sites reported with any incidence of wound infection. Additionally, scarring was identified in 5 cases (9.6%) in the collagen dressing site with average VSS score of 12 and 3 cases (5.8%) in the insulin dressing site with average VSS score of 10 indicating better clinical outcome in insulin gel group as compared to collagen dressing group.

DISCUSSION

Facial soft tissue injuries pose unique challenges due to their visibility on face, potential for scarring, and functional implications.^[11,12] Treating facial soft tissue injuries with appropriate dressing materials is paramount due to the unique anatomical and functional considerations of the face. Effective wound management not only promotes optimal healing outcomes but also significantly impacts esthetic and functional recovery. Effective wound management strategies are crucial to optimize healing outcomes and minimize esthetic and functional sequelae.^[13,14] Insulin and collagen dressings have emerged as promising therapeutic modalities, each offering distinct mechanisms of action and potential benefits in promoting wound healing. For instance, studies have highlighted the efficacy of insulin dressings in accelerating wound healing through their proliferative and anti-inflammatory effects.^[15-18] Similarly, collagen dressings have demonstrated their ability to enhance tissue regeneration and improve cosmesis by providing a supportive matrix for cell proliferation and migration.^[19,20] Choosing the appropriate dressing material should be guided by the specific characteristics of the wound, including its location, size, and depth, to ensure Table 1 Wound area comparison in both the dressing materials Intervention Insulin Gel Collagen.

Dressing

Day 0

N 52.00 52.00

Median 24.25 14.00

Std. Deviation 18.63 9.22

Day 3

N 52.00 52.00

Median 16.60 10.85

Std. Deviation 14.19 6.41

Day 7

N 52.00 52.00

Median 10.90 7.50

Std. Deviation 8.94 4.05

Day 14

N 52.00 52.00

Median 3.00 3.15

Std. Deviation 4.83 2.70

Day 21

N 52.00 52.00

Median 0.00 0.00

Std. Deviation 1.02 1.73

Table 2 Relative change in wound area in both the dressing materials Intervention Day 3 (%) Day 7 (%) Day 14 (%) Day 21 (%) Insulin gel -31.55% -55.08% -87.62% -100% Collagen dressing -22.50% -46.43% -77.50% -100% optimal outcome and patient satisfaction in the management of facial soft tissue injuries.

In this split face design experimental study, collagen membrane and insulin gel dressings were topically applied to all facial wounds in patients till the epithelization of wound was completed. To evaluate wound care compli- ance, healing rate, and complications, the two dressing materials used in this study were compared. Study by Mehreen et al. in 2019 compared the effectiveness of topical insulin with conventional povidone iodine dress- ings in frequency of healing of diabetic foot ulcers, where they reported signifcant diference in contraction of initial wound size among both the study groups depicting greater reduction in wound size in the insulin group but later both the groups showed similar frequency of healing.^[4,21] Study conducted by Radwa. M. Ali et al. in 2020 showed that topical insulin was both efective and safe for diferent wound types in diabetic patients. When comparing topical

insulin groups to the standard wound dressing, statistically significant differences were noted in the rate of wound healing suggestive of topical insulin dressing has superior healing property over the other dressing materials.^[9] In a comparative clinical study conducted by Munoyath et al. in 2015, it was found that amniotic membrane preserves a healthy excised wound due to its excellent adherence; minimizes the risk of infection; decreases loss of protein, electrolytes, fluids, and energy; minimizes pain; accelerates epithelial regeneration; and esthetically results in reduced scar formation when compared to collagen membrane.^[1,22]

In the present study, the insulin site showed significant initial healing compared to collagen dressing site but on day 21 both the sites were epithelized completely indicating adequate wound healing. It was observed that insulin had very good initial rate of healing by early epithelisation and minimizing the chances of wound infection. Scarring was found in 5 (9.6%) cases in collagen dressing site with VSS score of 12 and 3 (5.8%) cases in insulin dressing site with VSS score of 10.

Both insulin and collagen dressings offer unique advantages in managing facial soft tissue injuries.^[23,24] Collagen membrane being the standard form of dressing material showed good granulation tissue formation, maintaining a moist wound environment, and supporting overall wound healing in sensitive facial areas.^[25] In the present study, although the area of the wound that was allocated for the insulin gel site was much greater compared to the collagen dressing site, insulin gel dressings resulted in excellent accelerated wound healing with minimal inflammation, providing better antimicrobial effects and minimal scarring of the wound compared to collagen.

CONCLUSION

There are numerous commercial dressing materials available, some of them are considerably expensive for patients who seek cost-effective solutions. Topical Insulin as dressing material may be a superior option as it is inexpensive and readily available. Paucity of literature using insulin in treating facial soft tissue injuries made us to conduct this study and based on results, we recommend using insulin gel application over the facial wound to provide satisfactory healing. Also looking forward in conducting similar experiments in diabetic patients with facial injuries. Insulin being a growth factor with no harm to cellular system, one can even think about formulation of various delivery systems such as insulin nanoparticles, scaffolds and various other targeted delivery systems.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest The author(s) affirms no potential of conflicts of interest.

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